

OPEN EARTH MONITOR

D8.1 Open-Earth-Monitor official website

Document overview

Project	Open-Earth-Monitor (OEMC)
Project, full title	A cyberinfrastructure to accelerate uptake of environmental information and help build user communities at European and global levels
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Summary

The official Open-Earth-Monitor-Cyberinfrastructure website was published in June, 2022. The url is: <https://earthmonitor.org/>

Please find below screenshots made on 31 - 8 - 2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101059548.

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OPEN-EARTH-MONITOR PROJECT

We aim to connect user communities with Big Earth Data

Open-Earth-Monitor is a EU-Horizon Europe funded project that aims at building an open-source cyberinfrastructure to accelerate uptake of environmental information and help build user communities at European and global levels.

Starting date: 1st of June 2022

... Learn more

HYBRID EVENT

Why join this public workshop?

Discover the Open-Earth-Monitor project values and explore how you can become central in the design and testing of the first FAIR-cyber infrastructure. Seize the chance to network and connect with international organizations!

+ Register!

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Keynote speakers

"EuroGEO related project portfolio"

Erwin Goor

Project Officer, Environmental observation at European Commission REA

[LinkedIn](#)

"Anchoring Open-Earth-Monitor to the twin transition"

Jean Dusart

Policy Officer at the European Commission DG Research & Innovation

[LinkedIn](#)

"Earth Observation Land Data & Services beyond 2022"

Joanna Ruiter

Advisor Satellite Applications at the Netherlands Space Office

[LinkedIn](#)

"Need for environmental observation data: working with the private sector and investors"

Dagmar Mooij

Program Manager LDN TAF at IDH - The Sustainable Trade Initiative

[LinkedIn](#)

"Global land cover and land use monitoring"

Matt Hansen

Co-Director at the Global Land Analysis & Discovery University of Maryland

[Website](#)

"Open knowledge to bridge the digital divide"

Yana Gevorgyan

Director at Group on Earth Observations Secretariat

[Website](#)

"EO Platforms and open science in support of Green Deal ambitions"

Patrick Griffiths

European Space Agency Technical Officer

[Website](#)

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OPEN-EARTH-MONITOR PROJECT LAUNCH [Register via Eventbrite](#)

What to expect

Connecting data science to the ground

We want to build bridges connecting (Big) Earth Observation Data with the real world. How do we turn useful environmental information into action? **Follow our live feedback throughout!**

How to produce and release FAIR environmental data?

We aim to facilitate the uptake of environmental information for everyone by making data easier to access, understand and use. **Ask, discuss, suggest: Let's find out how.**

Enabling bottom-up governance for environmental data

Discover how people and their stories from the ground are vital to effectively monitoring Earth and land changes. **Connect, explore and be part of the early user-testing!**

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Research institutes, private businesses and public organizations: Meet our partners

Get in touch!

If you wish to collaborate or have any questions about the event, please [contact us](#).

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01-June-2022 to 01-June-2025

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A cyberinfrastructure to accelerate uptake of environmental information and help build user communities at European and global levels

Open-Earth-Monitor

The mission of Open-Earth-Monitor is to accelerate uptake of environmental information to guide current and future users in research, decision-making and citizens toward the most sustainable solutions.

Earth Observation technology is at the forefront of our efforts in solving the climate crisis

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Project objectives

That will be used to develop a general framework for increasing uptake and accessibility/exploitability of environmental observation information.

Produce an inventory of user needs, data and knowledge

In access for European stakeholders to existing European and global environmental observation data and actionable information.

Achieve notable and permanent improvement

to enable targeted end-users to monitor the status of natural resources at European and global scales, and production of environmental Business-2-Business solutions.

Produce a suite of intuitive tools

to enhance the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) of environmental observation data.

Build a comprehensive systematic platform

for processing and serving EarthObservation data, environmental in-situ-data, and Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and HPC models (OEMC-computing-engine).

Provide operational solutions

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Open-Earth-Monitor in a nutshell

- 22 Partner organizations
- Funding: 12,701,292.84 EUR
- 1 June 2022 - July 2026
- Call: (HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01)

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Working Packages

Open-Earth-Monitor is a multisectoral project and our consortium includes diverse partners, connecting European institutes at the frontier of data science and land monitoring.

WP1 — Project Management

WP2 — User-driven system design and FAIR workflow

WP3 — Open-Earth-Monitor computing engine

WP4 — Open-Earth-Monitor in-situ O&M usability tools

WP5 — Open-Earth-Monitor suite of tools to support EU programmes

WP6 — Open-Earth-Monitor suite of tools to support global programmes

WP7 — Business development and project sustainability

WP8 — Communication, dissemination and collaboration

This WP is dedicated to the organization and leadership of the project, organising project meetings, making action plans, discussing and distributing decisions, producing working and official project documents (technical and financial reports), and organizing the overall project management.

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The screenshot shows the Open Earth Monitor website interface. At the top left is the logo with a globe icon and the text "OPEN EARTH MONITOR". To the right are navigation links: "01 Home", "02 About", "03 Events", and a search icon. Below the logo is a search bar with the placeholder "Search for events" and a blue "Find Events" button. To the right of the search bar are tabs for "List", "Month", and "Day". Below the search bar is a date selector showing "Today" and "Now onwards". A message states "There are no upcoming events." Below this is a section titled "Latest Past Events". The first event is dated "JUL 19 2022" and titled "Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the EU Green Deal". It is a "VIRTUAL EVENT" held at "Forum Building Droeendaalsesteeg 2, Wageningen" on "July 19 @ 8h30 - 18h00". A small event poster is shown to the right. The second event is dated "JUN 1 2022" and titled "Registration deadline Open-Earth-Monitor Launch Event", held on "June 1 @ 8h00 - 17h00". On the left side, there is a "Dark Light" toggle. On the right side, there are social media icons for YouTube, Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter, with the text "Follow Us" below them.

Materials

This website was created using Wordpress, an open source software. It will be updated as the project continues.

Related tasks and outputs

The website will serve as the project's primary source of information dissemination for non-project members, including stakeholders and various end-users. Updates, events, blog posts and public reports will be accessible through this site, thus is an important foundational step for all work package 8 tasks, as well as outputs from other work packages.